

2-Carboxy-2'-hydroxy-4'-methylazobenzene as a Specific Spectrophotometric Reagent for the Estimation of Palladium(II) individually and also from Synthetic Mixture

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2-Carboxy-2'-hydroxy-4'-methylazobenzene¹ and 2-carboxy-2'-hydroxy-5'-methoxyazobenzene² have already been utilised effectively for the estimation of Pd^{II} spectrophotometrically. In course of the investigation it has been observed that the present reagent 2-carboxy-2'-hydroxy-4'-methylazobenzene is not only structurally simple compared to all other similar types of reagents found in literature causing the exposure of complexing zone easier to the metal ion, but also specific selective and reproducible. In addition, this reagent is more sensitive than other similar types of azodyes described in literature. Most of the cations and anions do not interfere. Palladium was estimated from the synthetic mixtures by solvent extraction at optimum pH of 8. The composition of the Pd-complex with this ligand remains in the ratio of 1 : 1 in solution and solid state.

Results and Discussion

Beer's law was obeyed in the range 1.25-3.7 ppm of Pd^{II}. The optimum concentration range as found from the Ringbom's plot was 1.53-3.25 ppm. The molar absorptivity of the complex as calculated from the Beer's law data and the photometric sensitivity according to Sandell³ were found to be $33.84 \times 10^3 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ at λ_{max} 560 nm and $0.0031 \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$ respectively. The 1 : 1 stoichiometry of the Pd^{II} complex was confirmed by Job's method of continuous variation⁴ and mole-ratio method⁵.

Among the ions, tartarate, citrate, oxalate, fluoride, molybdate, vanadate, ammonium, Cu^{II}, Mg^{II}, Ce^{III},

Cr^{III}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} do not interfere and Pb^{II}, Mn^{II}, Ag^I, Hg^I and Sn^{II} interfere in the estimation. Pt^{II}, Al^{III} and UO₂^{II} are tolerated upto 200, 150 and 100 ppm respectively.

Results of determination of Pd in synthetic mixture are presented in Table 1.

TABLE 1-DETERMINATION OF Pd^{II} IN SYSTEMATIC MIXTURES

Sample no.	Composition of mixture (in ppm)	Pd taken ppm	Pd found ppm
1.	Fe ^{III} (100), Co ^{II} (100), Ni ^{II} (200)	2	1.99
		4	3.98
		6	5.97
2.	Os ^{VIII} (50), Pt ^{II} (100), Ru ^{III} (100)	2.5	2.49
		3.5	3.48
		5.5	5.45
3.	Fe ^{III} (100), Ru ^{III} (100), Os ^{VIII} (50)	1	0.98
		3	2.99
		6	5.97
4.	Ni ^{II} (200), Pt ^{II} (100)	3	3.01
		5.5	5.49
5.	Fe ^{III} (100), Co ^{II} (100), Ni ^{II} (200), Ru ^{III} (100), Pt ^{II} (100)	1	0.98
		2	1.99
		3	2.89
		4	3.97
		5	4.99

Experimental

2-Carboxy-2'-hydroxy-4'-methylazobenzene was prepared by reported method⁶. The reagent solution (1 mg ml⁻¹) in absolute ethanol was used. The Pd^{II} solution was made from palladium chloride (AnalaR) and standardised by dimethyl glyoxime⁷.

Solutions of other cations and anions were prepared from AnalaR grade chemicals. Absorbance measurement was made with a Shimadzu UV 240 spectrophotometer. pH was determined with an Elico LI-10 pH meter.

Procedure : To an aliquot of Pd^{II} solution (1.6 ml; 0.025 mg ml⁻¹), the reagent solution (5 ml; 1 mg ml⁻¹) in ethanol was added followed by aqueous alcohol (10 ml). The pH of the mixture was adjusted to 8.0 by adding 10% sodium acetate solution and diluted to 25 ml to maintain the alcohol content of the final solution to 25% (v/v). The λ_{\max} of the purple coloured complex was found to be 560 nm against the reagent blank. The colour remained stable for more than 60 h. The measurement was made in 25% alcoholic (v/v) solution, required to keep the coloured species in solutions.

Determination of Pd^{II} from its synthetic mixtures : An aliquot of Pd^{II} solution (0.025 mg ml⁻¹) was taken and its pH was adjusted to 8.0 with 10% sodium acetate solution. A 0.1% (w/v) solution (5 ml) of the reagent in ethanol was then added to it and shaken for 5 min when purple colouration appeared. To it was then added isoamyl alcohol

(10 ml), shaken for 5 min, the phases were allowed to separate and the organic layer was dried over Na₂SO₄. The extraction was repeated with the isoamyl alcohol (2 × 5 ml) the combined extract was made up to 25 ml with isoamyl alcohol and its absorbance measured at 560 nm against reagent blank. The whole operation was repeated with only Pd^{II} solution and also with Pd^{II} solution mixed with fixed proportion of (i) Fe^{III}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, (ii) Os^{VIII}, Pt^{II}, Ru^{III}, (iii) Fe^{III}, Ru^{III}, Os^{VIII} (iv) Ni^{II}, Pt^{II} and (v) Fe^{III}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Pt^{II}, Ru^{III} in each operation

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